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Managing Amelogenesis Imperfecta in the mixed dentition: A comprehensive approach

Introduction

Amelogenesis Imperfecta (AI) is a rare disease known to cause alterations of the structure and clinical appearance of enamel due to a single gene mutation. It represents developmental defects in the quantity as well as quality of the enamel of both deciduous and permanent dentition. The estimated prevalence of AI is lower than 0.5% according to international studies. Witkop and Sauk in 1989 classified AI into four major categories based on the phenotype. Those are hypoplastic type, hypocalcification type, hypomaturation type and hypoplasia-hypomaturation with taurodontism. Abnormalities of enamel result in dentine sensitivity, rapid tooth substance loss and unsightly appearance, leading to considerable esthetic and functional consequences for the patient as well as the clinician, making successful rehabilitation of the AI patient, a challenge.

The following case report presents multidisciplinary management of a pediatric patient with Hypoplastic Amelogenesis Imperfecta in mixed dentition.

Case report

An 8 year old boy was presented to Restorative Dentistry Unit B, Institute of Oral Health Maharagama complaining of unaesthetic appearance of his teeth from the time of the eruption. The parents were worried as there were incidences of the child getting teased at school due to unpleasant appearance of his teeth. The child also complained of recent pain from broken down lower back milk teeth. His medical history was insignificant. Tooth brushing was done by the child alone and he complained of sensitivity while brushing. There was no positive family history of discolored teeth.

The principles of prevention before intervention should be practiced during treatment planning.

Figure 1: Pre-treatment photographs

Figure 2: Dental panoramic Tomograph (DPT)

Generally, he was healthy looking. Extra-oral examination revealed right side submandibular lymphadenopathy. On intra-oral examination, reddish gingival flaps covered 26 and 84 roots. Enamel of all most all the teeth was damaged and had rough enamel surfaces to varying degrees. Some areas were completely devoid of enamel and the remaining enamel and dentine was dark yellowish. 31 and 41 were relatively unaffected. Significant tooth wear was evident in posterior teeth. 64, 65 and 75 had active dentinal caries while 74 and 85 was clinically pulp exposed with signs of periapical periodontitis. 84 was a septic root. Plaque and calculi were evident. (Figure 1)

Dental Panoramic Tomograph (DPT) confirmed the presence of a full complement of permanent teeth. Enamel appeared thin or absent in some areas of unerupted teeth but radiographic demarcation between enamel and dentine was evident. Large occlusal radiolucencies in 74, 85 and small retained root parts of 84 were visible. All premolars were located far below the alveolar crest. (Figure 2)

History, clinical examination and radiographic investigations led to the differential diagnoses of Amelogenesis Imperfecta, fluorosis and chronological hypoplasia with more possibility towards AI. Further, he had unrestorable 74, 85 and 84, dentinal caries 64, 65, 75 and dentine hypersensitivity.

Care plan consist of preventive, stabilization, definitive and maintenance phases. During the preventive phase, the vital role in plaque control was explained to the patient and oral hygiene instructions given. Fluoride varnish applied and desensitizing tooth paste & GC Tooth Mousse were prescribed for home use. Dietary counseling was done following dietary analysis. Caries risk assessment was carried out using Caries Risk Assessment form recommended by AAPD.

Behavior management was done by interacting with the child in a gentle manner. Full mouth scaling was done and caries on 64, 65, 75 and occlusal surfaces of permanent molars were restored with glass ionomer cement (GIC) as a temporary measure to prevent further loss of tooth substances, to improve oral hygiene maintenance and to reduce dentine sensitivity.

Definitive phase of treatment was initiated by placing preformed stainless steel crowns for permanent first molars, 55, 65 & 75 under local anesthesia. Composite veneering was done for permanent anteriors, deciduous canines and deciduous upper first molars. According to orthodontic opinion, extraction of unrestorable and symptomatic 74, 84 and 85 done and a lingual arch space maintainer was fixed to prevent undesirable effect of early deciduous tooth loss. (Figure 3) Histopathological investigation of extracted teeth confirmed the diagnosis as Amelogenesis Imperfecta- Hypoplastic type. (Figure 4)

Figure 3: Lingual arch space maintainer

Figure 4: Ground section of 85 showing thinning of enamel and absence of enamel in some areas

After the completion of active treatment, the child was put on maintenance phase. He was reviewed regularly & Fluoride varnish application was done. Eruption of permanent premolars was noted during 1 year review appointment. Erupting new premolars were also discolored and early restorative intervention was planned in future review visits. (Figure 6 & 7)

Figure 5: Post-treatment photographs at 1 year review appointment

Figure 6: Pre-treatment facial view

Figure 7: Post- treatment happy smile of the patient

Discussion

Challenges experienced by the dentist during treating a patient with AI include difficulty to etch or clean teeth without anesthesia, abnormal etch patterns, decreased bond strength of affected enamel and loss of inter-occlusal space due to rapid tooth surface loss. Multi-disciplinary approach and meticulous planning is crucial to address the problems the patient is facing but also to outstretch the lifespan of an already weakened dentition.

The principles of prevention before intervention should be practiced during treatment planning. Effective oral hygiene measures, dietary counseling and fluoride therapy are invaluable as preventive measures. Minimal intervention is always preferred during all stages of active treatment to preserve the precious remaining enamel. Direct composite restorations offer good aesthetics and survival rates despite the presence of suboptimal enamel in AI patients.

Even in a failure, those can be re-furbished, repaired or even replaced without a significant biological and financial cost. For children in primary and early mixed dentitions, Stainless steel crowns (SSC)s are considered as a good option for molars of both dentitions. Our patient, 74 and 85 required extraction as they were grossly broken and acted as plaque traps while remaining symptomatic. Lingual arch space maintainer is a fixed bilateral space maintainer which resists mesial movement of permanent first molars in cases where there is pre mature loss of multiple bilateral primary molars.

Conclusion

Rehabilitation of patients with AI requires early recognition, a multidisciplinary approach and meticulous planning. Poor quality and quantity of enamel makes it difficult to balance between the success of restorative options and the biological costs involved. Customized restorative care plan and regular follow-up are essential in achieving long term success.

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